
The Role of Libraries in National Education Policy (NEP) 2020

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Abstract:

Libraries play a crucial vital role in facilitating access to online programmes for teaching, research and extension activities. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes the role of libraries in integrating educational information and technology guiding users to access accurate information and adopting to changing the user needs.

This article deals with the role of libraries in the National Education policy 2020, which recognizes the need to incorporate technology in to library services, such as providing access to e-books, e-journals and other digital resources.

Keywords: *National Education Policy (NEP), Information Literacy, Information Technology, Digital repositories, National Digital Libraries (NDLI), GOI Government of India, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) etc.*

Introduction:

Establishment of digital collection, online reference services, digital repositories, online catalogues and information literacy initiatives are some of the library efforts to further education in the age of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Reference and Information services help users to access library resources, encourage the use of library materials and meet their information needs.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 stands as a transformative network aimed at redefining India's educational landscape. The National Education Policy (NEP), which has replaced the previous policy from 1986, is India's new educational system. The primary goal of National Education Policy (NEP) is to

transform the educational system for the better, starting in 2021. The role of libraries emerges as a cornerstone for fostering knowledge, intellectual growth and equitable access to information. Libraries, traditionally regarded as repositories of books, have evolved into dynamic hubs that only facilitate learning but also contribute significantly to the multifaceted goals outlined in National Education Policy (NEP).

Role of National Digital Library of India (NDLI) in NEP:

NDLI is a Government – funded initiative, primarily implemented by IIT Kharagpur and was started in 2015 by the Ministry of Education. The main aim of these digital libraries is to distribute digital learning resources nationwide. While the

National Education Policy (NEP). 2020 emphasises enabling the education sector and utilizing the potential of digital, accomplishing those goals still present a challenge.

Role of INFLIBNET in NEP:

- To promote and implement computerization of operations and services in libraries and information centers of the country, following a uniform standard.
- To evolve standards and uniform guidelines in techniques, methods, procedures, computers hardware and software, services and promote their adoption in actual practice by all libraries, in order to facilitate pooling, sharing and exchange of information towards optimal uses of resources and facilities.
- To provide reliable access to the document of libraries by creating an on-line union catalogue of serials, theses/ dissertations, books, monographs, and non-book materials in various libraries in India.
- To provide access to bibliographic information sources with citations, abstracts etc., through indigenously created databases of the Sectoral Information Centers of NISSAT, UGC Information centre, city networks and such others and by establishing gateways for on-line accessing of national and international databases held by national and international information networks and centers, respectively.
- To optimize information resource utilization through shared cataloguing,

inter-library loan service, catalogue production, collection development and thus avoiding duplication in acquisition to the extent possible.

- To enable users dispersed all over the country, irrespective of location and distance, to have to information regarding serials, theses/ dissertations, books monographic and non-book materials.
- To create databases of projects, institutions, specialists etc. for providing on-line information service.
- To encourage co-operation among libraries, documentation centers and information centers in the country. So that the resources can be pooled for the benefit for helping the weaker resource centers by stronger ones.
- To train and develop human resources in the field of computerized library operations and networking to establish, manage and sustain INFLIBNET.

Role of Libraries in National Education Policy:

“Books are the Quietest and Most Constant Friends, They are the Most Accessible and Widest of Counselors and the Most Patient of Teachers.”- Charles W. Eliot

Today’s libraries have assumed a new role in modern society, whereby they integrate educational information and communication technology and new media. The role of academic libraries/ librarians in the information age to promote access to appropriate and accurate information to meet the needs of users. Internet is a wonderful thing but it is not a substitute for library premises. Librarians guide and teach

students and other users how to find the best sources of information, whether in print or online. A few years back libraries were book centric institutions. They were print just card catalogue. Libraries were known as the storehouse of knowledge/ information, but now a days concept of libraries has been changed. They collect books and non book materials and provide effective library services to their customers. All types of primary, secondary and tertiary sources of information are available in the college libraries. Some college libraries also have online search facilities and to provide Web 2.0 facilities. Web 2.0 (Library2.0) is a user centered virtual community. It is socially rich, often egalitarian electronic space. It is a modern form of library services that reflects a transition in the way services are provided to users within the library world.

National Policy on Library and Information System:

The department of culture, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India appointed a committee of senior library scientists and other experts in October 1985, which included Prof. Dr. D. P. Chattopadhyay as a chairman to prepare a draft document on National Policy on Library and Information System. Its report is titled National Policy on Library and Information System (NAPLIS). The committee completed its work and submitted a draft document to the Government on 31st May 1986. The main objectives of the library and information policy are recommended as follows.

- To promote and maintain the organization, availability and speed of

information in all areas of national activity.

- To take steps for modernization and upgradation of existing library and information systems and services and to introduce new programmes relevant to our national needs.
- To encourage programmers and initiate at the earliest possible pace the training of library and information personnel.
- To establish and adequate monitoring mechanism to ensure rapid development of library and information facilities and services to meet the information needs of all sectors.

Conclusion:

Libraries are the service institution; the basic concept of library is related to the service provided as per the need of the users. Libraries plan their programs based on the guidelines of the five laws of library science. Libraries have shifted from micro documents to macro documents. The function of libraries is not only to collect books and non-book materials and to provide effective library services but also to make the collection and dissemination more widely and rapidly through the variety of information services to its customers. With the changing nature of users' needs the libraries are also changing in the current environment. These are getting updated according to the needs of the users. Nowadays the concept of libraries has been changed. They have advanced a lot. Libraries themselves are shifting from traditional libraries to digital or virtual libraries.

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